

Green Colloidal Synthesis of MoS₂ Nanoflakes

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Currently, two approaches dominate the large-scale production of MoS₂: liquid-phase exfoliation, referred to as top-down approach, and bottom-up colloidal synthesis from molecular precursors. Known colloidal synthesis approaches utilize toxic precursors. Here, an alternative, green route for bottom-up synthesis of MoS₂ nanoflakes (NFs) is described. The NFs were synthesized by colloidal synthesis using [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ and a series of sulfur (S-) precursors including Thioacetamide (TAA), 3-Mercaptopropionic acid (3-MPA), L-cysteine (L-CYS), Mercaptosuccinic acid (MSA), 11-Mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA), 1-Dodecanethiol (DDTH) and Di-tert-butyl disulfide (DTBD). While TAA, a S-precursor most commonly used for MoS₂ NF preparation, is a known carcinogen, the other investigated S-precursors have low or no known toxicity. High-resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM), Grazing Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS) confirmed that in all cases the syntheses yielded single layer MoS₂ NFs with lateral sizes smaller than 15 nm and well-defined crystal structure. Electronic absorption and Raman spectra show the characteristic features associated with the MoS₂ monolayers. The evolution of the absorption spectra of the growth solution during the syntheses reveals how the kinetics of the NF formation is affected by the S-precursor as well as the nature of the coordinating ligands.

INTRODUCTION

Two-dimensional transition-metal chalcogenides (2D-TMCs) with a general composition MX₂, where M is a transition metal such as Mo or W and X = S, Se, or Te, are currently intensely studied group of materials.¹⁻⁴ Among the 2D-TMCs, the semiconductor MoS₂ is one of the most extensively investigated. This is, in part, due to the unusual stacking confinement behavior of the MoS₂, which shows a gradual transformation from an indirect bandgap material with a bandgap $E_g = 0.9$ eV in bulk, to a direct bandgap material with $E_g = 1.8$ eV in a single-monolayer.⁵⁻⁷ Unusual electronic properties of single- and few monolayers thick MoS₂ make it an appealing material for exploitation in optoelectronics, catalysis, energy storage and other areas.⁸⁻¹⁴

Large area single- or multi-layer MoS₂ sheets have been traditionally prepared by chemical vapor deposition (CVD), or by a liquid, mechanical or ion-intercalation exfoliation from bulk MoS₂.¹⁵⁻²⁰ Structures with lateral dimensions smaller than hundred nanometers, MoS₂ nanosheets, nanoplatelets or nanoflakes (NFs), can be prepared by breakdown of exfoliated MoS₂ sheets using various “top-down” approaches,²¹ by sol-thermal process,^{22, 23} or by CVD methods.^{24, 25} A limitation of these approaches is that they often suffer from limited reproducibility and large structural polydispersity of the produced NFs, particularly for nanometer size structures.²⁶

Scheme 1. (a) Synthetic approach used in the synthesis of the MoS₂ nanoflakes (NFs). (b) Structures of the used sulfur precursors.

Alternatively, MoS₂ NFs can be prepared by “bottom-up” methods, most notably colloidal syntheses.^{26, 27} This approach allows for tuning of the NF lateral sizes and stacking confinement down to the atomic scale level. Previously reported colloidal method for preparation of MoS₂ NFs are based on a reaction of toxic molybdenum compound such as CS₂, [Mo(CO)₆] or MoCl₅ with toxic sulfur compound such as thioacetamide (TAA) or hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS). The other limiting factor for these compounds is their instability towards air or moisture in certain cases.^{26, 28-30} The most commonly used colloidal synthesis method for preparation of MoS₂ NFs is based on a reaction of [Mo(CO)₆] with thioacetamide (TAA).^{26, 28} When heated, TAA releases hydrogen sulfide upon reaction with water³¹ or amines.³² This makes TAA a versatile S-source for the preparation of chalcogenide thin films³³ or nano-heterostructures.³⁴ A drawback of this approach is that both the [Mo(CO)₆] and TAA are toxic compounds.³⁵⁻³⁷ In search for less toxic routes for MoS₂ colloidal synthesis, Zhou et al.,²⁶ substituted [Mo(CO)₆] by low toxicity [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂, but in combination with TAA. In another example, 11-dodecanethiol was used as the less toxic S-source, but only in combination with the [Mo(CO)₆].²⁸ In yet another example, (NH₄)₂MoS₄ was explored as a less toxic source of both Mo and S.²⁷

In this work, we more systematically investigate the preparation of MoS₂ by colloidal synthesis, using a range of low-toxicity sulfur precursors and [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ as the Mo source. We investigate the effect of the sulfur precursor (and other reaction parameters) on the layer stacking, lateral dimensions, crystal structure, morphology, and optical properties of MoS₂ NFs as well as the dynamics of NF growth. The synthetic approach and the precursors used in the present work as well as prior reports, are graphically summarized in Scheme 1. In the present work, in a typical synthesis (0.03 mmol) [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ and (0.6 mmol) stearic acid was dissolved in a mixture of 6 g (15.5 mmol) trioctylphosphine-oxide (TOPO) and 6 mL (15.5 mmol) oleylamine followed by deaeration and heating to 330 °C. Subsequently, 0.45 mL (0.18 mmol) of solution of an S-precursor dissolved in oleylamine (0.4 mol/L) and heated to 45 °C was injected via a gas-tight syringe. The reaction mixture was then heated at 320 °C for 1 hr. A more detailed description of the synthetic procedure is provided in the supporting information (SI).

To quantify the relative toxicity of the precursors, we used the available information on the lethal dose, specific organ toxicity and environmental toxicity categorization, published by the European Chemical Agency (ECHA)³⁸ and Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS).³⁹ This information is summarized in Tables S1-S3 in the SI. Of the seven precursors tested (Scheme 1b), only TAA is listed as a possible human carcinogen. Overall, L-cysteine (L-CYS) followed by di-tert-butyl disulfide (DTBD) are the least harmful S-precursors for humans as well as the environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). The atomic structure, composition and morphology of the prepared NFs were investigated by an aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy (ac-STEM), electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and a high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) imaging. The HAADF-STEM images of the NFs prepared using different S-precursors are shown in Fig. 1. The prepared NFs exhibit very irregular shapes with many interconnections, which makes it difficult to accurately determine the distribution of lateral sizes. Based on the analysis of dozens of NFs in each sample, the NF sizes are estimated to be in the range of 2 - 15

Figure 1. HAADF-STEM images of the MoS₂ NF products prepared using various S-sources: (a) TAA; (b) 3-MPA; (c) L-CYS; (d) MSA; (e) MUA; (f) DTTH; (g) DTBD. The insets show the Fourier Transform of the STEM images.

nm. Although the resolution was partially compromised by the contamination of samples by traces of unreacted reagents and solvent residues, typical hexagonal crystal structure and corresponding reflections in reciprocal space (FFT insets) are clearly visible in all samples. The measured spacings of the (100) planes are in a very good agreement with the literature value of $d(100) = 2.73 \text{ \AA}$, as well as with the known lattice parameters for the MoS₂.⁴⁰ Small observed deviations from this value are attributed exclusively to a sample drift.

To explore the possibility of the presence of multiple MoS₂ polymorphs^{41, 42} (i.e., 1T, 1H (2H-mono), 2H and 3R), several dozens of NFs were thoroughly examined in each sample in terms of their lattice structure. In all monolayer NFs only the thermodynamically favored 1H phase was identified, with no evidence of transversal displacement of one layer of sulfur atoms, characteristic for the 1T phase. The analysis of the areas with overlapping NFs revealed the presence of turbostratic stacked layer systems showing typical Moiré patterns (see e.g., Fig. 1c). These turbostratic structures formed during the drop-casting deposition of the MoS₂ dispersion prior to the microscopy analysis and likely do not represent the properties of the NFs in solution.

Elemental composition of the NFs was investigated by EELS spectroscopy. The results are summarized in Table 1. For all S-precursors, the calculated stoichiometries are consistent with the expected 1:2 Mo:S ratio. A slight excess of sulfur is attributed to unreacted traces of pristine or partially decomposed S-precursors. The chemical composition of the NFs was also investigated by a detailed analysis of the intensity profiles

Table 1. Summary of the EELS studies of the NFs.

S-Precursor	Mo [at. %]	S [at. %]	S:Mo ratio
TAA	28 ± 2	72 ± 7	2.6 ± 0.3
3-MPA	29 ± 3	71 ± 6	2.4 ± 0.3
L-CYS	31 ± 3	69 ± 6	2.2 ± 0.3
MSA	29 ± 3	71 ± 6	2.4 ± 0.3
MUA	26 ± 2	74 ± 7	2.8 ± 0.3
DTTH	27 ± 2	73 ± 7	2.7 ± 0.3
DTBD	28 ± 2	72 ± 7	2.6 ± 0.3

across the individual atomic columns in the HR-STEM images (see SI, Fig. S1). This analysis is possible in a high-resolution HAADF mode known as Z-contrast imaging, where the intensity of the HAADF signal is proportional to the total mass of the atoms in a given column,⁴³ thus providing a chemical sensitivity. Using this analysis, alternating Mo and S sites in each hexagon were clearly identified in all structures.⁴⁴ The simulations of the expected intensities for a monolayer MoS₂ were in excellent agreement with the experiment, confirming the MoS₂ composition of the NFs (see SI, Fig. S1).

Thanks to the spontaneous orientation of some NFs perpendicularly to the TEM grid, we were also able to characterize the thickness of the NFs and the interlayer distance between them using STEM imaging. Fig. 2 shows an example of three intensity profiles crossing such upright NF stacked layers found in the

sample prepared using MUA S-precursor. The thickness of the NFs, highlighted by the dashed rectangles, varies between 3 and 6 Å. Although this range is slightly above the literature value for the distance between sulfur atoms ($d(S-S) = 3.2 \text{ \AA}$) across a single MoS₂ monolayer,⁴⁵ it is far below the value of 9.7 Å, known for the double layer.⁴⁶ The higher values observed here can be attributed to an imperfect perpendicular orientation of the inspected NFs or to their bending. Nevertheless, the observed thicknesses strongly indicate the monolayer nature of the synthesized NFs. In the analysis of the stacked layers (SI, Fig. S2) we found that the interlayer spacing between two NFs is approximately 11 to 19 Å. This finding supports the above-mentioned turbostratic character and is consistent with the results of the X-ray scattering measurements discussed below. For comparison, the literature value for the interlayer spacing of multilayer MoS₂, 2H or 3R phase, is about 6.5 Å.⁴⁶ These results show that regardless of the S-precursor used, in all cases syntheses yielded a single layer 1H phase MoS₂ NFs with similar structural properties and morphology.

The structure of the NFs was also investigated by the Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The experimental data for the NFs prepared using the MSA S-precursor are shown in the SI, Fig. S5. We found that the AFM measurements were complicated by aggregation of the NFs. For the samples where the data could be analyzed, the measured NF thickness and size were consistent with the literature values for single-layer MoS₂ and with the results of the TEM analysis discussed above.

Grazing-Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering (GIWAXS).

In contrast to the direct space imaging of MoS₂ flakes using TEM, GIWAXS provides a complementary structural information averaged over a large ensemble of MoS₂ flakes. Fig. 3 shows a representative GIWAXS pattern for MoS₂ flakes prepared using an MSA as the S-precursor. As described in more detail in the experimental section (SI), the samples for the GIWAXS experiment were prepared by spontaneous drying of the dispersion following a drop-casting from an n-hexane

Figure 2. HAADF-STEM images (a) and (b) of the MoS₂ NF product prepared using MUA. Line intensity profiles across NF flakes oriented perpendicularly to substrate, profile (LP1) taken from the image (a) and profiles (LP2) and (LP3) taken from the image (b).

Figure 3. GIWAXS pattern of drop-casted MoS₂ MPLs prepared using MSA as the S-precursor.

solution onto a silicon substrate. As a result, we expect uniaxial anisotropy, meaning that the majority of MoS₂ flakes are aligned parallel to the underlying substrate.⁴⁷ This was confirmed by GIWAXS as the 100 diffraction is located along q_r axis ($q_r \sim 2.3 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$). The absence of strong 002 diffraction, which should be visible at $q_z \sim 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$, confirms that MoS₂ flakes are monolayers. The diffraction spot in the low reciprocal space at $q_z \sim 0.15 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ belongs to a lamellar stack of MoS₂ flakes. Assuming the thickness of the MoS₂ monolayer to be 0.7 nm, the calculated d-spacing of 4.3 nm of the lamellar stack is consistent with a thickness of the surfactant layer of 1.8 nm. Furthermore, a broader maximum at $q_z \sim 0.36 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ (d-spacing of 1.7 nm) with a lower orientation degree with respect to the surface normal is indicative of the stacked MoS₂ layers shown in TEM images (Fig. 2b). A slightly smaller monolayer thickness obtained by the HR-STEM is attributed to an extra vacuum annealing of the samples prior to the measurement. The GIWAXS patterns for all the MoS₂ flakes produced are shown in Fig. S4.

Electronic extinction/absorption spectra. The electronic extinction (absorption plus scattering) spectra of MoS₂ in the UV-vis-NIR spectral range are dominated by three distinct bands with peaks near 650 nm (1.9 eV), 600 nm (2.1 eV) and 400 nm (3.1 eV), typically labelled as A, B and C, respectively (Fig. 4). The low energy peaks A and B are associated with the band-edge excitonic transitions at the Γ point of the Brillouin zone, while the feature C is associated with the transition from the high density of states regions in the valence band to the conduction band in the Brillouin zone between the Λ and Γ points.^{48, 49} As was shown previously,^{47, 50} in thin-layer MoS₂, the intensities and positions of the A and B excitonic peaks provide an information about the lateral dimensions and the thickness of the MoS₂ sheets.

Specifically, the intensity of the B peak systematically increases with the lateral size of the sheet, while the peak wavelength of the A peak increases with the number of layers per nanosheet. In general, the electronic extinction spectra recorded for suspensions of MoS₂ solids contain significant contributions from the absorption as well as scattering, with very similar spectral profiles.⁵⁰ The relative contribution of the scattering to the overall extinction depends on the thickness as well as lateral size of the sheets. However, for the sheets with a thickness of a few monolayers and with lateral dimensions smaller than 50 nm, the scattering contribution is negligible.⁵⁰ Therefore, for the MoS₂ NFs prepared here, we attribute the measured extinction primarily to the electronic absorption.

The extinction spectra of the n-hexane suspensions of MoS₂ NFs prepared using all seven S-precursors are summarized in Fig. 4a. Following the method of Backes et al.,⁵⁰ the spectra were normalized at 345 nm (3.59 eV). While all three characteristic peaks, A, B, and C, are clearly discernible in all the spectra, the excitonic peaks A and B are significantly less pronounced than previously reported for bulk MoS₂ or larger MoS₂

Figure 4. (a) Electronic extinction/absorption spectra of the prepared MoS₂ NFs suspended in n-hexane. All spectra were normalized at 345 nm. (b) Variations in the position of the maximum of the excitonic peak A (empty circles) and the ratio of the extinction at the excitonic peak B and the extinction at 345 nm (solid triangles). The color coding is the same as in the legend of panel (a). (c) Changes in the absorption of the aliquots extracted at indicated times during synthesis of the MoS₂ NFs using MUA as an S-precursor. The spectra were normalized at 345 nm. (d) Variations in the ratios of the extinction at excitonic peak B and extinction at 345 nm (solid circles) and the excitonic peak C and extinction at 345 nm (empty squares) recorded for the absorption spectra of the aliquots collected at 10, 20, 30 and 60 min after start of the reaction. The color coding is the same as in the legend of panel (a).

flakes.⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰ There are several reasons for this. As mentioned above, for nanoflakes with lateral sizes on the order of hundred nanometers or more, the intensity of excitonic bands decreases systematically with the flake size.^{47, 50} This effect is even more pronounced for smaller structures.^{51, 52} In addition, since the reduction in size leads to the shifts in the position of the excitonic peaks,⁵⁰⁻⁵² increasing dispersion in size and/or shape of NFs causes broadening and increase in the overlap of the excitonic bands. With the high shape dispersity of most of the structures prepared here (see Fig. 1), a significant broadening of the excitonic bands is to be expected. Finally, for the MoS₂ structures smaller than one hundred nanometers, the optical properties are increasingly dominated by their edge states, excitonic character of which is dependent on specifics of the edge composition and morphology and can be quite different from the periodic lattice of the MoS₂.⁵¹ Backes et al.,⁵⁰ proposed that in thin layer MoS₂, the edge region is approximately 8 nm in size. That means that in the NFs smaller than 15 nm, the optical response is expected to be dominated by the electronic contributions from the NF edges.⁵⁰

Fig. 4b summarizes the variations in the maxima of the excitonic peak A (empty circles) and the ratios of the extinction at the excitonic peak B and at 345 nm (solid triangles) for the NFs prepared using all S-precursors. The position of the peak A was estimated using fitting of the extinction spectra with multiple Gaussian functions. The results show a relatively small variation in the peak position, with the maxima falling in the 600-650 nm range for all samples. This is lower than the peak positions observed for monolayer structures in the liquid-exfoliated nanosheets, where the excitonic peak was observed at wavelengths above 660 nm.⁵⁰ Although, in that work the analyses did not include nanostructures below 70 nm, the higher energies of the A excitonic peaks of the structures prepared here, suggest that they are likely comprising one or few monolayers. Furthermore, a comparison of the Ext_B/Ext₃₄₅ suggests that the NFs prepared using 3-MPA and DTTB likely have, on average, larger lateral sizes than structures prepared by TAA, while NFs prepared by other precursors are likely smaller than those prepared by using TAA.

Fig. 4c shows the evolution of the extinction spectrum of the NF growth solution during the reaction of the [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ with MUA. While the variations in the spectra are relatively small, there are clearly visible changes in the spectral regions around 400 and 600 nm. We attribute these changes to the formation and growth of the MoS₂ NFs. The analysis of the changes in the extinction spectra observed during the reactions of all used precursors are summarized in Fig. 4d. To quantify the evolution of the absorption spectra, we show changes in the ratio Ext₆₀₅/Ext₃₄₅ (solid circles), used in previous studies,^{47, 50} as well as a new parameter Ext₃₉₉/Ext₃₄₅ (empty squares). The evolution of the spectra allows a qualitative estimate of the relative rate of the NF formation with various precursors. The results suggest that for the NFs prepared using TAA, DTBD, MUA and DTTB continuously grow at a similar rate during the monitored time period. During the same time period, the NFs prepared using MSA and L-CYS undergo little change and the NFs prepared using 3-MPA seem to undergo a reduction in size. In terms of dynamics, the most rapid growth during the monitored period is observed for NFs prepared using DTTB and MUA. Based on the relative intensities of the B and C peaks at the first measured datapoint at 10 min, we can tentatively divide the S-precursors into two categories: 1) quickly reacting S-sources (TAA, DTBD, 3-MPA) and 2) slowly reacting (MSA, MUA, L-CYS, DTTB). We attribute these differences to a different mechanism of sulfur release from an S-source. Specifically, quickly reacting sulfur sources release sulfur at lower

temperatures, while slowly reacting sulfur sources need higher temperatures and a longer time to release sulfur. This is consistent with the available Thermogravimetry Analysis (TGA) data showing the temperature onset of thermal decomposition for DTBD (below 180 °C),⁵³ TAA (100 °C)⁵⁴ on one hand and for DDTH (230 °C),⁵⁵ L-CYS (210 °C),⁵⁶ and MUA (200 °C),⁵⁷ on the other hand.

Raman spectroscopy. Raman spectroscopy is a well-established method for characterization of the vibrational properties as well as morphology of MoS₂ crystallites. The Raman spectrum of bulk MoS₂ is characterized by two prominent peaks denoted as E¹_{2g} (~383 cm⁻¹) and A_{1g} (~409 cm⁻¹), associated with in-plane and out-of-plane lattice vibrations, respectively.^{58, 59} In addition to serving as an evidence for formation of MoS₂ crystal lattice, an important feature of the two vibrational modes is that their frequencies and frequency differences vary with the crystallite thickness.⁶⁰ For large MoS₂ flakes with lateral sizes tens of nanometers to micrometers, the E¹_{2g} band shifts to higher energies with the decreasing number of MoS₂ layers, while at the same time the A_{1g} band shifts to lower energies. As a result, the peak-to-peak separation gradually decreases from $\Delta\nu \sim 26$ cm⁻¹ in bulk to $\Delta\nu \sim 19$ cm⁻¹ for a single layer MoS₂.⁶⁰ Thus, in large MoS₂ flakes, the separation between the E¹_{2g} and the A_{1g} bands can be used to identify the number of layers comprising the crystallite. However, in studies of single-layer MoS₂ nanostructures prepared by ion-bombardment,⁶¹ simulating an effect of structural defects, it was shown that for NFs smaller than approximately 10 nm, the reduction in NF size leads to an opposite effect, where the E¹_{2g} band downshifts while the A_{1g} band upshifts and $\Delta\nu$ increases. This has been attributed to a lateral phonon confinement.⁶¹ As a result, in small NFs, the E¹_{2g} band can be observed at frequencies as low as 381 cm⁻¹ and A_{1g} band at 407 cm⁻¹, with $\Delta\nu$ as high as 27 cm⁻¹. We note that the E¹_{2g} and A_{1g} peak positions

Figure 5. (a) Raman spectra of the prepared MoS₂ NFs drop-casted from n-hexane solution on glass cover slips. The excitation wavelength was 405 nm (b) Peaks positions and frequency differences for E¹_{2g} and A_{1g} modes as a function of the S-precursor used in the NF synthesis.

can be also affected by other factors, such as doping, strain or dielectric environment.⁶² Raman spectra of the MoS₂ NFs prepared in this work are shown in Fig. 5a. The spectra obtained using 405 nm laser excitation possess two prominent peaks near 380 cm⁻¹ and 405 cm⁻¹ attributed to the E_{12g} and A_{1g} Raman modes, respectively. This observation is consistent with the formation of the MoS₂ crystalline lattice. Fig. 5b shows the specific peak positions and peak-to-peak separations for the NFs prepared by investigated S-precursors. The position of the E_{12g} mode varies with the S-precursor in the range from 380.5 to 383.4 cm⁻¹, while the A_{1g} mode varies in the range from 403.7 to 406.4 cm⁻¹. The peak-to-peak separation varies from Δν = 23.0 to 23.7 cm⁻¹. The peak positions as well as the value Δν are in good agreement with the values previously observed for strongly laterally confined single-layer MoS₂ nanostructures.⁶¹ Since the HR-TEM and GIWAXS results discussed above show that the prepared NFs are mostly single-layer structures, we conclude that the Raman spectra of NFs prepared by all of the S-precursors are dominated by contributions from single-layer NFs with a significant lateral phonon confinement.

Effects of ligands on the MoS₂ NFs growth. Our studies of the MoS₂ NF growth under various reaction conditions show that ligand NF growth dynamics is highly sensitive even to the smallest variations in the composition and structure of the ligand used in growth solution. As one example, Fig. 6 summarizes the effect of several variations in the composition of the ligand environment on the dynamics of the NF growth for reactions using the DTBD as an S-precursor. The figure shows the changes in the extinction spectra of the aliquots of the MoS₂ NFs in n-hexane collected at 10, 20, 30 and 60 min after the S-precursor injection.

In panel (a) is shown the evolution of the extinction spectra for the reaction where the NFs were stabilized by

Figure 6. Absorption spectra monitoring evolution of MoS₂ in different ligand environments. Growth of MoS₂ in mixture containing: (a) TOPO (99%), oleylamine (OAm) (80-90%), stearic acid (SA) (97%); (b) Technical TOPO (90%), oleylamine (OAm) (80-90%), stearic acid (SA) (97%); (c) TOPO (99%), octadecylamine (ODA) (90%), stearic acid (97%); (d) TOPO (99%), oleylamine (OAm) (80-90%), lauric acid (LA) (99.5%).

Triethylphosphine-oxide (TOPO) (99%, 15.5 mmol), oleylamine (OAm) (80-90%, technical grade, 15.5 mmol) and Stearic Acid (SA) (97%, 0.6 mmol). The results show that in this ligand environment, the NF formation, as indicated by the formation of distinct A, B and C peaks, is nearly complete within 10 min. Panel (b) shows the extinction spectra of the aliquots for the reaction performed under identical conditions, but with using a technical grade TOPO (90%), instead of TOPO with higher 99% purity. As can be seen in the figure, in this case the spectra show no indication of NF formation. The main impurities in technical grade TOPO are phosphonic acid, phosphorous acid, dioctylphosphinic acid, octyl-1,8-diphosphinic acid, dioctylphosphine oxide and dioctylphosphinic acid.^{63,64} In previous studies of CdSe NCs, it was shown that these impurities can significantly affect the kinetics of the growth of the NCs, mainly due to a coordination of the phosphonates and phosphinates to Cd²⁺.⁶⁵ Since our results indicate that in the case of MoS₂, the impurities completely inhibit the NF formation, we hypothesize that the complexation of the phosphonates and phosphinates to Mo²⁺ is stronger than in the case of Cd²⁺. Panel (c) shows the evolution of the absorption spectra for the reaction similar to the one shown in panel (a) but with OAm substituted with octadecylamine (90%, technical grade) (ODA). In this case, the main difference is the change from an amine containing a single carbon-carbon double bond (OAm) to a fully saturated version of the amine with the same chain length, with 18 carbons. Our results show that even such a small variation in one of the ligands dramatically reduces the reaction kinetics, with the first appearance of the C peak feature in the extinction spectrum after 60 min. We attribute the observed difference primarily to the presence of the C=C bond in the OAm, which allows it to function as a weakly coordinating ligand via the π-orbitals of the C=C bond. Such coordination was previously reported to influence the growth of nanocrystals and their crystallinity and morphology.^{66,67} We note that since the purities of the OAm and ODA are technical grade, the other contributing factor to the difference in observed reaction kinetics could be a different content of the impurities. Panel (d) shows the evolution of the absorption spectra for the ligand environment similar to the one shown in panel (a) but with OAm substituted with the Stearic Acid (SA) substituted with Lauric Acid (LA). Based on the smaller prominence of the features in the spectra region C and A, B, in panel (d), compared to panel (a), we conclude that in the presence of the shorter LA the NF formation is slower than in the presence of longer SA. We note that the NF synthesis was performed at 320°C, which is above the boiling point of LA (~300°C),⁶⁸ but below the boiling point of SA (~360°C).⁶⁹ This means that while significant amount of SA is likely to be present in the growth solution during the synthesis, this is not the case for the LA. Thus, the stabilization of the metal monomers typically accomplished by the fatty acids,⁶⁸ is absent in the case of LA, which leads to the less favorable kinetics of the NF growth. Overall, our observations suggest that ligands that can stabilize the Mo monomers have likely a positive effect on the dynamics of the MoS₂ formation.

Although, the available data provides a limited direct information about the reaction mechanism of the MoS₂ growth, the available evidence suggests that the reaction likely proceeds in the following sequence. In the first step, the Mo-fatty acid complex is formed from the [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ at 330 °C. For the fatty acids with lower boiling point, the complex formation is less efficient, which reduces the Mo reactivity in the following step. Following the injection of the sulfur precursor in oleylamine, the Sulphur precursor rapidly decomposes releasing the elemental Sulphur. Although, the Sulphur release is generally

rapid, the rate varies with the type of the precursor. This is followed by the MoS₂ crystal growth along the (002) plane.

CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrated that single-layer MoS₂ NFs with lateral sizes smaller than 15 nm can be effectively prepared by colloidal synthesis by reacting [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ with a series of S-precursors with low toxicity. Our results indicate that the demonstrated synthetic approach is general, allowing for a wider exploration of the S-precursors in the synthesis of MoS₂ NFs, as a step towards their broader practical applicability. We found that the kinetics of the reactions are sensitive not only to the S-precursor, but also to the coordinating ligands used in the reactions. More systematic studies of the ligand and precursor effects may lead to the development of synthetic schemes, which will allow better control over the shape, size and crystallinity of the MoS₂ NFs. These studies are currently in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and methods. Molybdenum(II) acetate dimer (purity 98 %), Di-tert-butyl disulfide (DTBD, purity 97 %), 3-Mercaptopropionic acid (3-MPA, purity 98 %), Mercaptosuccinic acid (MSA, purity 97 %), 11-Mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA, purity 95 %), Thioacetamide (TAA, purity 98 %), 1-Dodecanethiol (DDTH, purity ≥98 %), Stearic acid (SA, purity 97 %), Lauric Acid (LA, purity 99.5 %), Octadecylamine (ODA, purity 90 %, technical grade), Oleylamine (OAm, purity 80-90 %, technical grade), Trioctylphosphine-oxide (TOPO, purity 99 %; technical grade purity 90 %) and n-Hexane (Emplura, ACS grade) were purchased from Merck and used without further purification. L-cysteine (L-CYS, Serva Entwicklungslabor Heidelberg, p.a. grade), Isopropanol (VWR, p.a. grade) were purchased and used without any further purifications. Argon (6.0 grade, purity 99.9999 %) was purchased from Messer Tatra-gas.

Synthetic procedures. All reactions were performed on greaseless Schlenk line under argon atmosphere. The reaction temperature was maintained and monitored using DigiSense (Cole Parmer) temperature controllers. Sulfur precursor was prepared by dissolving an S-precursor in OAm to reach concentration 0.4 mol/L. Solution with the precursor was heated to 50 °C under continuous argon flow for 1.5 h. The mixture containing [Mo(CH₃COO)₂]₂ (0.0128 g; 0.03 mmol), stearic acid (0.1707 g; 0.6 mmol), TOPO (6 g; 15.5 mmol) and oleylamine (6 mL; 15.5 mmol) was heated to 65 °C under continuous flow of argon for 1.5 h. The Mo precursor solution was then subjected to three vacuum/argon refill cycles at 120 °C and subsequently heated to 330 °C. At this temperature, 0.45 mL of sulfur precursor solution was injected via a gas-tight syringe. The reaction mixture was then heated for one hour at 320 °C. Evolution of the MoS₂ nanocrystals was monitored by removing aliquots (1 mL) from reaction mixture at regular intervals, at 10, 20, 30 and 60 minutes after injection. Obtained aliquots were immediately quenched/diluted in hexanes and used for optical measurements without any purification. The reaction was stopped after 60 minutes by removing a heating mantle. Small amount of the cooled growth solution was dispersed in n-hexane. MoS₂ nanocrystals were subsequently precipitated with isopropanol and isolated from the suspension by centrifugation (6000 rpm, 150 seconds). The isolated precipitate was re-dispersed in n-hexane for further characterization.

HR-STEM measurements. Structural and elemental analysis was carried out using an aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM) JEM-ARM200cF (JEOL) operated at a low acceleration voltage of 80 kV to avoid sample

damage.⁴⁴ For STEM imaging, the probe convergence semi-angle was set to 11.2 mrad. High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) detector's inner and outer semi-angles were 45 and 180 mrad, respectively. EELS elemental analysis was done using a Gatan GIF 965 Quantum ER camera equipped with a fast-Dual EELS system. EELS collection semi-angle was to 29.3 mrad. The energy dispersion was set at 0.25 eV/channel. All acquired data were processed with 64-bit Digital Micrograph GMS 3.21 (Gatan). The NFs dispersed in n-hexane solution were drop-casted on ultra-thin carbon TEM grid (400 mesh Cu) followed by IR lamp drying. HAADF-STEM image simulation was done by software JEMS (SI, Fig. S1).⁷⁰

GIWAXS measurements. The samples for the GIWAXs experiment were prepared by drop-casting of the n-hexane solution of washed NFs onto a silicon substrate. The grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) measurements were performed at table-top home-made GIWAXS set-up. The used X-ray source is a microfocus X-ray source with focusing Montel optics (1μS, Incoatec, Germany) generating CuKα radiation (E = 8.04 keV, λ = 1.54 Å). The photon flux of the X-ray source is 3×10⁸ photons/s. The focal spot size on the sample was 250 μm (FWHM). The GIWAXS patterns were recorded by a single photon counting 2D X-ray detector (Pilatus 100K, Dectris, Switzerland). The pixel size is 172 x 172 μm² (H x V). The X-ray beam impinged on the sample at a shallow angle of incidence of 0.2°. The sample-detector distance was set to 75 mm. The exposure time for recording a single GIWAXS pattern was 30 min. Before the sample, the guarding slit was placed to reduce X-ray scattering from the air.

Absorption spectroscopy. Absorption spectra of n-hexane solutions of MoS₂ NFs were collected using Agilent 8453 diode-array spectrometer using 1 cm quartz cells.

Raman Spectroscopy. Raman measurements were performed using a Raman system alpha 300R from Witec with excitation wavelengths of 405 nm at ambient conditions. The samples were prepared by dropcasting n-hexane solution of NFs on glass cover slip. The excitation laser (wavelength 405 nm) was focused on the sample with a 50× objective (NA = 0.8). The laser power was below 1 mW. Raman spectra were collected by an ultra-high throughput spectrometer (UHTS, Witec) using a grating of 1800 gr/mm and detected by a cooled CCD camera with an integration time of 5s averaging several locations.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Precursors toxicity characteristics, supporting TEM results, supporting GIWAXS results are included in Supporting Information. This material is available free of charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Notes

There are no conflicts to declare.

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Synopsis. MoS₂ nanoflakes were synthesized by bottom-up colloidal synthesis using a series of low toxicity precursors. The analysis of the products by High-resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy, Grazing Incidence Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering confirmed that in all cases the syntheses yielded single layer MoS₂ nanoplatelets with lateral sizes smaller than 15 nm and well-defined crystal structure. Electronic absorption and Raman spectra show the characteristic features associated with the MoS₂ monolayers and provide insights about the growth kinetics.

